

Project CHANGES- Spoke 4

D2 – Data Management Plan: first version – v1.0

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Spoke information

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No	Name	Acronym	Role
1	Alma Mater Studiorum – Università di Bologna	UNIBO	Spoke leader
2	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa	UNISOB	Spoke co-leader
3	Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche	CRN	Member
4	DTC Lazio	DTC	Member
5	Engineering	ENG	Member
6	Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro	UNIBA	Member
7	Università degli Studi di Ferrara	UNIFE	Affiliated by "convenzione"
8	Università degli Studi di Firenze	UNIFI	Member
9	Università degli Studi di Parma	UNIPR	Affiliated by "convenzione"
10	Università degli Studi di Torino	UNITO	Member

Executive Summary

The activities of Spoke 4 - *Virtual Technologies for museums and art collections* focus on the impact of digital cultural heritage (DHC), compared to the current views on tangible and intangible heritage. The final objective is to make the digital enhancement of cultural heritage a permanent and widespread practice in museums and art collections, in order to:

- Increase the knowledge and organization of artifacts in all forms
- Expand the general public involvement
- Improve and make more sustainable the exhibition potential
- Improve accessibility, inclusiveness, participation, enjoyment and sustainability.

This Data Management Plan describes the categories of data that will be/is being produced by the project and details how they will be handled in a transparent manner and according to FAIR principles.

This deliverable is a living document and will evolve during the lifespan of the project: new updated versions have already been planned for month M15 and M27. In addition, the DMP will be updated whenever important changes to data management or data management policy occur.

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1. Introduction

The participants to Spoke 4 – *Virtual Technologies for museums and art collections* met online (via Microsoft Teams) on 21 April 2023 to discuss Research Data Management (RDM) in the context of the Spoke's activities. The consortium discussed how to implement an efficient RDM strategy in line with FAIR principle and open science practices. After a brief introduction on FAIR RDM tools and practices in the context of Digital Cultural Heritage (DCH), the structure and purpose of this Data Management Plan (DMP) was discussed. The group agreed on a common strategy to draft and revise this document.

This deliverable is a living document and will evolve during the lifespan of the project: new updated versions have already been planned for month M15 and M27. In addition, the DMP will be updated whenever important changes to data management or data management policy occur.

2. Data Summary

The activities of Spoke 4 focus on the impact of digital cultural heritage (DHC), compared to the current views on tangible and intangible heritage. The final objective is to make the digital enhancement of cultural heritage a permanent and widespread practice in museums and art collections, in order to:

- Increase the knowledge and organization of artifacts in all forms
- Expand the general public involvement
- Improve and make more sustainable the exhibition potential
- Improve accessibility, inclusiveness, participation, enjoyment and sustainability.

In addition, in line with the objectives of the NRRP¹, the project will:

¹ National Recovery and Resilience Plan, <https://www.italiadomani.gov.it/content/sogei-ng/it/en/home.html>

- Reinforce multidisciplinary research on a topic of strategic value
- Introduce innovative models for basic research, promoting synergies between universities, cultural heritage institutions and companies (through the implementation of pilot studies involving national museums and art collections)
- Empower existing research infrastructures and support innovation by developing specific competences to address the needs of cultural heritage institutions and companies working on DHC.

Table 1 below provides and overviews the **categories of data** that the project will generate and re-use; some examples are provided where possible, as well as the **file formats** the data will be stored and disseminated in.

Table 1: Overview of the types and formats of data that the project will generate and re-use

Types of data	Examples	Formats
3D models	e.g., 3D models containing geometry, material and texture information	glTF, GLB, obj, mtl, png, tiff, jpg, e57
Images	e.g., digital reproductions of manuscripts, digital reproductions of artworks, acquired and processed photos, panoramas	tiff, png, jpg, raw
Tabular	e.g., tourist flows related to cultural places, questionnaire answers	csv
Textual	e.g., excerpts from literary texts, semi-structured interviews but also newly produced texts like papers and publicity material	pdf, txt
Audio	e.g., interviews, music, interactive guides	mp3
Video		mp4, mov
Other	e.g., metadata	RDF formats (e.g., ttl, nt, nq, jsonld)

For a detailed list of the dataset that the Spoke partners plan to produce and re-use in the context of the project, please see [Annex I](#).

Considering the potentially high number of high-resolution images, 3D models and videos, the **expected size of several datasets is in the terabyte range**. Each partner will manage their own data, and at this stage it does not seem necessary to budget for extra storage space.

3. FAIR data

3.1. Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

According to FAIR principles², all data produced during the course of the project will have associated metadata and persistent unique identifiers (PIDs)³ assigned as early as possible. If existing data and metadata (e.g., from museums and galleries) have already been assigned a PID, this is always used to refer and point to the data.

Decisions on **metadata standards** may take into accounts schemas adopted by museums and galleries chosen as templates but, in any case, follow existing standards widely used in the cultural heritage sector. At a minimum, the findability of each dataset is insured through the provision of general-purpose metadata (e.g., Dublin Core, DataCite) via the repositories chosen for long term preservation.

During data collection and analysis, each partner takes care of hosting their data on **GDPR-compliant cloud services** that provide **automatic versioning** (e.g., OneDrive). Software is developed on discipline-specific platforms that also provide built-in versioning (e.g., GitHub). For other types of data, clear version numbers are provided within the file names, in the form:

```
filename_with_underscores_DDMMYYYY.extension
```

² <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/>

³ Such as DOIs (for most digital objects), and Software Heritage ID (for software)

as indicated in the Spoke coordination guide. This ensures transparent research management, helps collaboration, and minimises the risks of losing or overwriting files and data.

3.2. Making data accessible

The table below outlines which data repositories have been selected to ensure continued accessibility to the datasets generated in the course of the project (see also [Annex I](#)). **Most datasets will be openly available**, while others will be shared with some restrictions (see also the section [Increase data re-use](#) below).

Table 2: List of datasets with relative repository for long-term preservation and access license

N	Summary description of content	Repository	License	Reasons for controlling access
1	3D models of curved surfaces	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
2	3D models of small objects	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
3	3D models and images	Zenodo	CC BY-SA 4.0	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
4	Images, 3D models, audio-visual files	to be decided	to be decided	The reasons will be included, if applicable
5	Raster and vectorial images, 3D Models	to be decided	to be decided	The reasons will be included, if applicable
6	Images, texts, tabular files	Zenodo	CC 0	
7	Images, texts, tabular files	Zenodo	CC 0	
8	Excerpts from literary texts, tabular files	Zenodo	CC 0	
9	Excerpts from literary texts, tabular files	Zenodo	CC 0	
10	Texts	Zenodo	CC 0	
11	Texts (publicity material)	Zenodo	CC 0	
12	Interview transcripts	Zenodo	CC 0, when possible	Where possible and appropriate, the content that emerged from the interviews will be made openly available. In some cases, confidentiality may be required and the related materials may

				remain for the exclusive use of the research team.
13	Tabular files (tourist flows)	Zenodo	CC 0	
14	Questionnaires	Zenodo	not accessible (controlled/closed access)	The data contained in the questionnaires will remain for the exclusive use of the research team.
15	Texts (brochure, articles, catalogues, general documents)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
16	Audio (podcast, interview, music, interactive guide)	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
17	3D models and photogrammetric images	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
18	Images, Gigapixel images	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
19	Video	Zenodo	CC BY 4.0	
20	Metadata	Zenodo	CC 0	
21	Raster Images, 3D models, data specification for transmission of 3D scenes and models	Zenodo	CC 0, when possible	Some models may require a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions or the person owning the original object.
22	Raster Images, 3D models, data specification for transmission of 3D scenes and models	Zenodo	CC 0	

At this stage, almost all partners have opted for depositing data in **Zenodo**⁴, a generalist data repository funded by the EU which guarantees long term preservation, attributes DOIs to all archived datasets and all versions, supports open licenses and different access levels. It complies with OpenAIRE requirements for data archives, meaning that the project datasets will also be visible via the OpenAIRE portal. Zenodo also allows users to create specific pages

⁴ <https://zenodo.org/>

dedicated to all research outputs from a specific project or a community; the page dedicated to the Spoke is available at: <https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/>

Going forward, it is possible other data repositories will be used alongside or in place of Zenodo, ideally following a review of discipline-specific data archival infrastructures.

3.3. Making data interoperable

The interoperability of project data and technologies – their “ability to work together with other systems”⁵ – will be pursued on all levels. This will help scaling up and deploying solutions across cultural institutions and will promote the creation of “an ecosystem of services” for CH.

The very first step is to use **standard formats for all the types of data we generate** (see [Table 1](#)) as not to be bound to any proprietary software applications. When specific pay-for software is used during data collection and analysis (e.g., MS Word, Excel), files are exported to open formats (e.g., .txt, .rtf, .pdf) to **facilitate exchange and re-use** and **guarantee long-term preservation**. Regarding 3D formats, an interoperable open standard⁶ targeting interactive Web3D applications, is the glTF. The adoption of such standard will guarantee high interoperability with existing 3D platforms/services, re-use and also integration of licensing information inside the format.

Further, CH data is collected, analysed and otherwise treated with in mind **existing guidelines**, such as those published by the Italian Ministry of Culture in the context of the *Piano nazionale di digitalizzazione del patrimonio culturale (PND)*⁷, and the *Cultural Heritage Data Reuse Charter*⁸.

⁵ <https://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/interoperability>

⁶ Now ISO standard - <https://www.iso.org/standard/83990.html>

⁷ <https://digitallibrary.cultura.gov.it/il-piano/>; <https://docs.italia.it/italia/icdp/>

⁸ <https://datacharter.hypotheses.org/77>

Commonly used **controlled vocabularies and ontologies** (e.g., CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model⁹) will be adopted whenever possible; otherwise, an explanation will be provided together with rich documentation. If ontologies or controlled vocabularies are produced as part of the project, they will be described in this DMP to facilitate their reuse.¹⁰

The methodologies and workflows used for data collection and analysis, including for the production of FAIR-compliant data, will be thoroughly documented. Equally, all software and data deposited in a repository will be accompanied by the relevant documentation – i.e., all information necessary to evaluate, understand and reuse it – in the form of a README file or similar.

3.4. Increase data re-use

Please see [Table 2 above](#) for a list of the envisioned datasets and relative access license. If the data cannot be shared openly, an explanation is provided in the rightmost column.

The majority of datasets will be released under the most permissive Creative Commons licenses, CC 0¹¹ e CC BY¹², in line with Open Science and with the commitment of making publicly-funded research data “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”. In a few cases, a more restrictive license may be required, to protect personal data or to comply with

⁹ “The CIDOC CRM represents an ‘ontology’ for cultural heritage information i.e. it describes in a formal language the explicit and implicit concepts and relations relevant to the documentation of cultural heritage. The primary role of the CIDOC CRM is to serve as a basis for mediation of cultural heritage information and thereby provide the semantic ‘glue’ needed to transform today’s disparate, localised information sources into a coherent and valuable global resource”. See <https://www.cidoc-crm.org/node/202>

¹⁰ Cfr. PND: <https://docs.italia.it/italia/icdp/icdp-pnd-dmp-docs/it/v1.0-giugno-2022/scheda-progetto/open-data.html#ontologie-e-vocabolari-di-riferimento-i-c>

¹¹ <https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/>

¹² <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

existing intellectual property rights. At this stage, we do not anticipate applying any embargoes to the data we generate.

4. Allocation of resources

Data collection and analysis are integral to the Spoke activities and are covered by the effort of the people involved in the project.

At this stage, none of the partners has budgeted for extra storage space, while long-term preservation in Zenodo comes free of charge for dataset smaller than 50GB.

5. Data security

Partners store their data on GDPR-compliant cloud services. If personal data are collected in the course of the project, they are further protected (e.g., via file encryption) and never shared.

Research data stored in computers, laptops, intranets or hard-drives are accessible only after logging in with username and password (periodically modified according to national law provisions for data security) and are protected by updated antiviruses.

Backup copies (ideally 2) of data and other files are routinely made and saved on different supports.

6. Ethics

Some project activities revolve around administering surveys/questionnaires to groups of people. **Informed consent forms** for participation in research and for sharing data will be included in each data collection task dealing with personal data. The information included in the forms needs to be accepted by all participants before the data collection may start.

Acceptance will be pursued by means of signature of participants or legal guardians, or by means of clicking on the relevant boxes for accepting terms and conditions of use.

As mentioned, all partners store their data on GDPR-compliant cloud services. If they collect personal data in the course of the project, they endeavor to **protect them further, for example via encryption**, and to **never share them** within anybody. Storage devices, such as laptops and memory sticks, are appropriately protected from unauthorized access and stored securely. When possible and appropriate, research data will be **anonymized** (e.g., cleaned of all personal data) and then shared with the consortium or the wider public. If relevant, we will describe here the anonymization process.

The activities of the Spoke involve complex intellectual property considerations. Each project partner is responsible for:

- **clearing all existing intellectual property rights** (e.g., when reproducing a copyrighted work of art, or reusing data from other projects), with the help of legal experts, if necessary
- make an informed decision, at the time of deposit at the latest, on the **type of reuse license to attach to the data they produce**.

Acknowledgements

We wish to thank all participants to WP1 for their collaboration in defining a research data management workflow for the project and in drafting this document. We are also extremely grateful to our external reviewers, Tiziana Mancinelli e Mario Marino, who read the document and provided precious feedback.

Annex I: Datasets

Thanks to the partners' input, we have carried out a census of the datasets that will be created or re-used in the context of the Spoke. Please bear in mind that the list below is provisional and will be updated throughout the project.

Dataset number	1
WP number	WP4
Creator	Montaldo, Silvano (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Oher contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	Changes WP4 SMA01
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	3D Models of curved surfaces (scanned tattos)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	400G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	Lombroso Museum Catalogue

Dataset number	2
WP number	WP4
Creator	Pennacini, Cecilia (0000-0003-4626-4290)
Oher contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	Changes WP4 SMA02
The data set is	re-used
Status	in progress

Data types	3D models of small objects (3D models, laser scans and tomographies)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	100G
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	

Dataset number	3
WP number	WP4
Creator	Montaldo, Silvano (0000-0003-0820-8730)
Oher contributor/s	Amitrano, Cristina; Damiano, Rossana; Mensa, Enrico
Rights holder/s	University of Turin
Dataset title	Changes WP4 SMA03
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	3D and 2D Models (informal art objects; drawing, paintings, other artefacts)
Data formats	glTF, GLB, jpeg, tiff; other suitable formats will be taken into account at a later stage of the research
Dataset size	400g
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY-SA 4.0, "Attribution-ShareAlike", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-sa/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	Ethical reasons may limit reuse
Related output	Lombroso Museum Catalogue

Dataset number	4
WP number	WP4
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Oher contributor/s	Montanari, Roberto

Rights holder/s	Università degli Studi Suor Orsola Benincasa; Ente morale Istituto Suor Orsola Benincasa
Dataset title	SMA UNISOB PLATFORM
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Digital objects included in the platform are mostly high-resolution images in 2D. Some of these are also expected to be in 3D. Moreover, together with images also audio-visual files are expected. All these materials are going to be considered for responsive web-based platform.
Data formats	So far, the data expected to be used for the platform are mostly web-based delivery format such as JPG, gif, png for images. For 3D the most suitable format is under evaluation, as well as for media files (i.e., audio-visual).
Dataset size	The calculation of the Dataset size is in progress. Current estimation is approximately between 500 giga and 1,5 Terabyte.
Repository	The Repository system is under evaluation in accordance with the IT infrastructure responsible of the Institution.
License	The license is under evaluation and not yet defined
Reasons for limiting access	The reasons will be included, if applicable
Related output	

Dataset number	5
WP number	WP4
Creator	Genovese, Gianluca (0000-0002-1064-2061)
Other contributor/s	Maffei, Tiziana; Montanari, Roberto
Rights holder/s	Reggia di Caserta
Dataset title	Reggia di Caserta digital environment
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	not yet available

Data types	Digital objects included in the platform are mostly high-resolution images. Mostly in 2D dimension: some of these images are expected to be also 3D, most of them are going to be considered for responsive web-based platform and the therefore vectorial.
Data formats	So far, the data expected to be used for the platform are mostly web-based delivery format such as JPG, gif, png for images. For 3D the most suitable format is under evaluation, as well as for media files (i.e., audio-visual).
Dataset size	The calculation of the Dataset size is in progress.
Repository	The Repository system is under evaluation in accordance with the IT infrastructure responsible of the Institution.
License	The license is under evaluation and not yet defined
Reasons for limiting access	The reasons will be included, if applicable
Related output	

Dataset number	6
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana (0000-0001-8469-2814)
Oher contributor/s	Pescarin, Sofia; Villani, Paola; Gasperina Geroni, Riccardo; Stracuzzi, Riccardo
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna National Research Council - Roma
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Digital reproduction Carlo Levi's pictures and manuscripts
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Photographs, Text, Tabular
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	7
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WP number	WP4
Creator	Stracuzzi, Riccardo (0000-0001-9730-6820)
Oher contributor/s	Pescarin, Sofia; Villani, Paola
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna National Research Council - Roma
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Digital reproduction of Grazia Deledda's manuscripts
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Photographs, Text, Tabular
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	8
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana (0000-0001-8469-2814)
Oher contributor/s	Gasperina Geroni, Riccardo; Villani, Paola; Stracuzzi, Riccardo
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Selection of excerpts from Carlo Levi's literary texts
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Text, Tabular
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/

Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	9
WP number	WP4
Creator	Stracuzzi Riccardo (0000-0001-9730-6820)
Oher contributor/s	Benvenuti, Giuliana; Battilani, Patrizia; Villani, Paola
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Selection of excerpts from Grazia Deledda' literary texts
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Text, Tabular
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	10
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana
Oher contributor/s	All partecipants
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna National Research Conucil - Rome
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Publication of papers on literary parks
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available

Data types	Documents printed or on-line
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g.,.txt, .pdf), Web
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	All other datasets will be used for these publications.

Dataset number	11
WP number	WP4
Creator	Benvenuti, Giuliana (0000-0001-8469-2814)
Oher contributor/s	All partecipants
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna National Research Council - Roma
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Flyers and brochures for dissemination events
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Documents printed or on-line
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g.,.txt, .pdf), Web
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	All other datasets will be used for these flyers and brochures.

Dataset number	12
WP number	WP4
Creator	Bagnaresi, Davide (0000-0002-7093-7283)

Oher contributor/s	Battilani, Patrizia
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Semi-structured interviews aimed at learning about the tourism characteristics of the area and gathering suggestions about the figures of Carlo Levi and Grazia Deledda
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Text
Data formats	MS Word format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC0, when possible
Reasons for limiting access	Where possible and appropriate, the content that emerged from the interviews will be made openly available. In some cases, confidentiality may be required and the related materials may remain for the exclusive use of the research team. They will be processed in accordance with privacy regulations. Should it be decided to formulate a questionnaire, the questionnaire data may also remain confidential.
Related output	

Dataset number	13
WP number	WP4
Creator	Bagnaresi, Davide (0000-0002-7093-7283)
Oher contributor/s	Battilani, Patrizia
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Provincial and local tourist flows related to cultural places (e.g., house museums) directly related to the Carlo Levi and Grazia Deledda literary parks.
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	Tabular
Data formats	Excel format, exported to exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)

License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	14
WP number	WP4
Creator	Stracuzzi, Riccardo
Other contributor/s	
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	CHANGES, WP 4, Questionnaires for school stakeholders regarding the Carlo Levi and Grazia Deledda literary parks
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Textual, tabular
Data formats	MS Word and Excel formats, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .txt, .pdf, or similar), Excel format, exported to open standard format for preservation (e.g., .csv)
Dataset size	It will not be necessary to include extra storage space in the budget.
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	not accessible (controlled/closed access)
Reasons for limiting access	The data contained in the questionnaires will remain for the exclusive use of the research team.
Related output	

Dataset number	15
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Other contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467); De Mauro, Lara (0009-0003-3460-024X)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - Università di Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_TEXT, v001
The data set is	re-used; new;
Status	in progress

Data types	Forms, brochure, articles, catalogues, educational book, monographs, general documents
Data formats	PDF
Dataset size	5 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	16
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Oher contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467); De Mauro, Lara (0009-0003-3460-024X)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italy
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_AUDIO, v001
The data set is	re-used; new;
Status	not yet available
Data types	Podcast, interview, music, interactive guide
Data formats	mp3
Dataset size	1 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	17
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Oher contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467); De Mauro, Lara (0009-0003-3460-024X)

Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_3D, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	3D projects, 3D models, photogrammetric images
Data formats	obj, pdf, jpeg
Dataset size	12 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	18
WP number	WP4
Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Oher contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467); De Mauro, Lara (0009-0003-3460-024X)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_IMAGES, v001
The data set is	re-used; new
Status	in progress
Data types	Images, Gigapixel images
Data formats	jpeg, tiff, png
Dataset size	7 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	19
WP number	WP4

Creator	Thun Hohenstein, Ursula (0000-0003-2835-3679)
Oher contributor/s	Parisi, Chiara (0009-0005-6887-2467); De Mauro, Lara (0009-0003-3460-024X)
Rights holder/s	Sistema Museale di Ateneo - University of Ferrara, Italia
Dataset title	CHANGES - SPOKE 4, WP1, SMA_ML_VIDEO,v001
The data set is	re-used; new;
Status	in progress
Data types	Video
Data formats	mp4, mov
Dataset size	5 terabyte
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC BY 4.0, "Attribution", https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	

Dataset number	20
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305)
Oher contributor/s	Barzaghi, Sebastian; Daquino, Marilena; Heibi, Ivan; Massari, Arcangelo; Moretti, Arianna; Tomasi, Francesca
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna
Dataset title	Metadata of collections in University of Bologna's Museums
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	Metadata
Data formats	RDF (following the CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model)
Dataset size	MB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/

Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The datasets related to the acquisition and 3d modelling of the event "THE OTHER RENAISSANCE - Ulisse Aldrovandi and the wonders of the world" (21) and the museum Giovanni Capellini (22)

Dataset number	21
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305)
Other contributor/s	Apollonio, Fabrizio Ivan; Balzani, Roberto; Barzaghi, Sebastian; Bitelli, Gabriele; Bonifazi, Federica; Bordignon, Alice; Cipriani, Luca; Colitti, Simona; Collina, Federica; Fanini, Bruno; Fantini, Filippo; Ferdani, Daniele; Fiorini, Giulia; Formia, Elena Maria; Forte, Anna; Giacomini, Federica; Girelli, Valentina Alena; Iannucci, Alessandro; Manganelli Del Fa, Rachele; Pescarin, Sofia; Ronchi, Diego; Sullini, Mattia; Tini, Maria Alessandra; Travaglini, Laura; Vittuari, Luca; Zambruno, Simone
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Italian National Research Council
Dataset title	Raster images, 3D Models and Data Specification of the exhibition "THE OTHER RENAISSANCE - Ulisse Aldrovandi and the wonders of the world"
The data set is	new
Status	in progress
Data types	1. Raster Images (acquired and processed photos, panoramas) 2. 3D Models, containing geometry, material and texture information (exported from Photogrammetric/Scanner software) 3. Data Specification, for efficient transmission of 3D scenes and models targeting Web3D applications.
Data formats	1. *.jpg, *.raw - e.g. *.nef (Nikon), *.crw (Canon), *.arw (Sony), and *.raf (Fuji) 2. *.obj, *.mtl, *.png, *.tiff, *.jpg, *.e57 3. *.glTF, *.glb - when exporting: UVs, Normals e Vertex color, with "Compression" if available
Dataset size	GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC0, when possible

Reasons for limiting access	It may be possible that, for some models, we need to specify a different license depending on the restrictions of the cultural heritage institutions or the person owning the original object.
Related output	The metadata describing all the objects of the exhibition (20).

Dataset number	22
WP number	WP4
Creator	Peroni, Silvio (0000-0003-0530-4305)
Other contributor/s	Apollonio, Fabrizio Ivan; Balzani, Roberto; Barzaghi, Sebastian; Bitelli, Gabriele; Bonifazi, Federica; Bordignon, Alice; Cipriani, Luca; Colitti, Simona; Collina, Federica; Fanini, Bruno; Fantini, Filippo; Ferdani, Daniele; Fiorini, Giulia; Formia, Elena Maria; Forte, Anna; Giacomini, Federica; Girelli, Valentina Alena; Iannucci, Alessandro; Manganelli Del Fa, Rachele; Pescarin, Sofia; Ronchi, Diego; Sullini, Mattia; Tini, Maria Alessandra; Travaglini, Laura; Vittuari, Luca; Zambruno, Simone
Rights holder/s	Alma Mater Studiorum - Università di Bologna Italian National Research Council
Dataset title	Raster images, 3D Models and Data Specification of the museum Giovanni Capellini
The data set is	new
Status	not yet available
Data types	1. Raster Images (acquired and processed photos, panoramas) 2. 3D Models, containing geometry, material and texture information (exported from Photogrammetric/Scanner software) 3. Data Specification, for efficient transmission of 3D scenes and models targeting Web3D applications.
Data formats	1. *.jpg, *.raw - e.g. *.nef (Nikon), *.crw (Canon), *.arw (Sony), and *.raf (Fuji) 2. *.obj, *.mtl, *.png, *.tiff, *.jpg, *.e57 3. *.glTF, *.glb - when exporting: UVs, Normals e Vertex color, with "Compression" if available
Dataset size	GB
Repository	Zenodo (https://zenodo.org/communities/pe5-spoke4/)
License	CC 0, "No Rights Reserved", https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/public-domain/cc0/
Reasons for limiting access	
Related output	The metadata describing all the objects of the exhibition (20).